

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

TRANSFORMATION OF OPERATIONAL ACTIVITIES AS AN ECONOMIC AND MANAGEMENT INNOVATION OF MODERN ORGANIZATIONS: METHODOLOGICAL ASPECT

Akselrod R.

*PhD, Associate Professor of the Department of Political Science
Kyiv National University of Construction and Architecture, Ukraine
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Abstract

The article is devoted to solving the scientific task of developing theoretical and methodological provisions and providing methodological and applied recommendations for improving approaches to economic evaluation and substantiation of projects of construction enterprises based on the postulates of value engineering and process-oriented management. The relevance of scientific research is due to the need to implement a large-scale program of updating the technical and technological base of most domestic enterprises on the basis of replacing outdated types of equipment, technologies and models of construction production management, as well as improving the economic and management methodical approaches of the organization and administration of the enterprise. Especially in the current conditions, when the key task for any company is to reduce costs, both at the construction stage and during the operation of the facility. Value engineering of investment and construction projects is closely related to concepts such as: project risk management, complex project cost management, construction object life cycle management, since the operational (economic) activity of a construction enterprise is the realization of the stages of construction project implementation. From our point of view, a comprehensive evaluation of the transformation of operational activity should be carried out according to a certain algorithm of coordinated actions, which are systematized by blocks: a preparatory block, the main part of the study and a resulting block with elements of forecasting the further development of the enterprise as an open operating system and its level of competitiveness.

Keywords: *change management, investment project cost management, transformation project investment evaluation, construction cost formation, construction enterprise.*

Awareness of the content and regularities of globalization, the growth of the scale of transnationalization, and within it the intensification of competition create not only economic, political and other problems for ensuring the overall economic acceleration in the state. But they also generate opportunities for the comprehensive expansion of inter-industry ties and access to foreign markets of national product manufacturers. It is objective to recognize that in order to reduce the susceptibility of the national economy to external threats and internal risks, the goal-oriented implementation of the declared innovative model of economic development has the priority of solving the problems of forming and introducing into business practice an effective economic mechanism of inter-industry participants (stakeholders) interaction on the platform of implementation of transformation projects operational activity, since the operational (business) activity of a construction enterprise is the realization of the stages of implementation of a construction project [1].

Regarding the implementation of the policy of inter-sectoral cooperation in construction projects under conditions of resource limitations, the implementation of the specified strategic management tools for the Ukrainian economy is a difficult task both in the internal socio-economic environment and at the level of project stakeholders. Since, ensuring a sufficient level of competitiveness of business entities and their products faces administrative and forceful actions and "opportunities" of rapidly changing political elites in Ukraine.

Therefore, comprehensive measures in this area are reduced, mainly, to the implementation of:

a) technical and economic evaluations of projects as a type of state (public) investment, determination of levels of competitiveness;

b) cost-free innovations related to updating the personnel potential of production and economic systems, etc. [2-4]. At the current historical stage of the development of the national economy, the experience of solving problems related to increasing the efficiency of functioning due to the consolidation of inter-sectoral interaction at different levels of economic regulation is not used. At the same time, the target programs for the development of public-private partnership as a type of economic activity in Ukraine, developed by the subjects of state administration, do not allow: a) to identify the phase trajectory of their dynamics in the context of their acquisition of information features; b) to activate and carry out fundamental transformational processes in the field of construction in order to eliminate the threats arising in connection with the intensification of competition in the specified field of industrial and economic activity.

In addition, modern institutional mechanisms and legal support for the processes of restructuring the Ukrainian economy do not enable the formation of organizational and economic prerequisites for solving most of the economic problems that exist in the construction industry. This determines: a) steady degradation of the progressive sphere of social activity; b) large-scale losses of the strategic resource of industrial

growth and underdevelopment of the state's intellectual capital; c) low product quality and efficiency of innovative and production processes in construction. And also the fact that according to most indicators of the level of competitiveness, the construction industry of Ukraine remains at the bottom [5-7]. This requires the urgent implementation of organizational and economic change mechanisms for the forced development of domestic construction enterprises with: a) taking into account international achievements in this field of activity and national economic interests; b) ensuring close cross-sectoral interaction and structural transformations in accordance with the requirements of project implementation [8].

On the basis of the conducted research, the generalized system of indicators of the efficiency of the operational activity of the enterprise, which most thoroughly characterizes the main parameters of the efficiency of the operational system of the construction enterprise, can be combined within four approaches:

1) resource-based, when the economic result is compared with the economic assessment of production resources used during production;

2) cost-effective, when the economic result is compared with the current costs that are directly related to its achievement;

3) resource-intensive, which, as can be seen from the name itself, is a certain compromise between the two previous ones. That is, both a certain assessment of available resources and an assessment of current costs are taken into account. However, the application of this approach should be very balanced and careful, because there is a problem of double counting, as well as a significant influence of industry specifics of production (capital intensity, capital intensity, labor intensity, etc.;

4) target, when efficiency is defined as the degree of achievement of the target parameters of the enterprise's functioning, and therefore the result and the target value of the indicator are set in the same units of measurement [9-13].

This system includes indicators, the values of which are calculated both on the basis of internal management accounting information and on the basis of the results of special hardware and statistical measurements, which makes it possible to comprehensively assess the effectiveness of the use of both elements and the effectiveness of the operation of the enterprise's operating system as a whole.

The next stage is the planning and implementation of measures to increase the efficiency of the company's operational activities. The main problem in the process of finding possible ways to optimize the operation of the enterprise's operating system is the complexity of its structure and component content, which ensures the complexity of formalization and optimization of the main processes, without losing essential characteristics and relationships that ensure the normal functioning of the enterprise.

Among the main ways of increasing the efficiency of the enterprise's operational activity, three can be distinguished, aimed at increasing the above-mentioned indicators: organizational, technical and technological, and resource [9].

Within the organizational direction, the search for opportunities to improve the efficiency of those processes taking place at the enterprise is carried out by identifying and restructuring (or optimizing) inefficient operational processes that do not create value for the external and/or internal customer.

As a result of such measures, the enterprise gets the opportunity to use potential reserves of increased labor productivity (as a result of shortening the processes of the operational cycle in time), reduction of production and management costs, which as a result of the cumulative effect will open opportunities for increasing the efficiency of the operational activities of this enterprise (Table 1).

Table 1.

The results of the effectiveness of the implementation of innovative tools

The effect of use	Expected cost reduction,%
Reduction of energy consumption. Optimization of utilities. <i>By identifying and analyzing the most expensive consumers, cases of wasteful use of energy</i>	2–10
Reduction of energy consumption costs. Use of utilities through peak load management. <i>Management of energy-consuming consumers to avoid unnecessary peak loads</i>	5–20
Confirmation, documentation of energy consumption. <i>Minimize the cost of creating consumption reports through the use of data on objects and meters from the system</i>	50–90
Reduce documentation costs. <i>Thanks to fast systematization of information, use of templates, direct access of reports to actual data</i>	30–70
Reducing the cost of searching, improving the quality of information. <i>Reducing the cost of finding and providing up-to-date and correct information, reducing problems with insufficient and erroneous information</i>	30–70
Equipment availability. <i>Reducing the number of failures of equipment and structures due to automated control of service life</i>	1–10
Scheduled maintenance. <i>Reduce the cost of scheduled maintenance and repairs through effective planning and preparation</i>	10–30
Distribution of outfits / tasks. <i>Reduction of service costs due to consolidated centralized accounting and distribution of correct orders / tasks (eg maintenance, cleaning)</i>	10–30

Changing not only the organizational structure of the enterprise and the work organization regulations, but also its sectoral and functional stakeholder-oriented structure, the transition to a qualitatively new level is both an end in itself and the result of transformational processes, a manifestation of transformational shifts, the achievement of which is possible when forming a model of transformational shifts based on an in-depth perspective analysis taking into account the institutional, technological and socio-economic prerequisites and interests of all groups of agents of the economic system, which is reflected in the author's model of transformational shifts, the mathematical content of which is the function $TCh \rightarrow \max (+)$:

$$TCh = f(TCh_{IS}; TCh_{TS}; TCh_{CES}), \quad (1)$$

where TCh – transformation shifts; TCh_{IS} - transformation changes of the institutional structure; TCh_{TS} - transformation changes of the technical-and-technological structure; TCh_{CES} -transformation changes of the social-and-economic structure.

The competitive environment forces companies to increase the efficiency of their operations by improving day-to-day operations and reducing non-productive activities. An effective tool in this case is the management concept called "process approach".

According to the latest research, 47% of the surveyed respondents report using a process approach. 34% of them are large holding companies, 53% are large and medium-sized state enterprises, and 13% are small enterprises.

The composition and content of business processes is determined based on the analysis of the enterprise's activities. The set of business processes depends on the types of products and services it produces or provides. When singling out and structuring business processes, it is necessary to consider them from the point

of view of completeness and the possibility of measuring the costs of their implementation.

The importance of business processes in the creation of products is not the same because of their different roles in the production process. Every enterprise has important and secondary processes.

When solving a problem related to the reengineering of business processes of an enterprise, it is necessary to identify:

1. What processes need to be improved;
2. What exactly needs to be improved in these processes.

Process improvement often requires significant time and financial resources to identify and implement improvements. Therefore, it should be carefully examined whether improving the given process is the most suitable solution to increase the ability to generate value before making the corresponding investment.

Major improvements in secondary processes usually do not lead to any significant results in the company's activity, while small improvements in important processes can significantly improve the company's performance.

Before reengineering business processes, it is necessary to determine:

- a set of those business processes that are related to the production of finished products;
- the most important business processes for the enterprise;
- bottlenecks in the implementation of these business processes.

Management of business processes, based on the process paradigm, includes four interrelated stages, which are presented in fig. 1:

Fig. 1. The sequence of implementation of the process paradigm of managing business processes (transformation of operational activities)

Each of the factors listed in formula 1 affects the defined goals, but has a different weight, the calculation of which is carried out through the previous procedure of ranking the factors with an assessment in points of each of them. Accordingly, on the basis of their assessment, a decision is made regarding the priority factors in the development of the BP business process project, which must be flexible and adaptable to changes in the internal management and external economic environment.

For each user, the information support system is evaluated from the point of view of achieving different, sometimes contradictory, goals that determine the internal structure of the business and its integration into the external economic environment. The goals must be properly structured, which is required by the logic of building information processes.

The value engineering system includes a number of subsystems that can be separated as independent systems (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. The structure of the cost engineering system in construction

The author proposes the calculation of the transformation index of the operational (economic) activity of a construction enterprise, which involves determining the main propulsive dominants of development in each individual case according to the following algorithm:

$$RCI_{Ti} = \sqrt[4]{\frac{InvI_{i(1)} \times InnovI_{i(1)} \times Intll_{i(1)} \times InfI_{i(1)}}{InvI_{i(0)} \times InnovI_{i(0)} \times Intll_{i(0)} \times InfI_{i(0)}}, (2)$$

where RCI_{Ti} – (Transformation index of competitiveness) is the transformation index of competitiveness of the i -th enterprise; $InvI_i$ (Investments index) – index of investment processes; $InnovI_i$ (Innovation index) – index of innovation processes; $Intll_i$ (Intellectualization index); $InfI_i$ (Informatization index); 0 – initial (base) period; 1 – the next period.

The operational activity transformation index is a complex multidimensional indicator that includes four main components that reflect each of the specified stages of the transformation of the operating system,

except for the initial stage of transformations, at which the second level is determined based on the use of the established and revealed resource-image potential. Thus, the proposed transformation index is an approach to determine the prerogative of investment, innovation, intellectualization, or informatization development of the particular enterprise being analyzed. Moreover, the transition to a new stage of transformations is impossible without achieving a certain level of competitiveness at the previous stage, just as it is impractical to move on to winning higher competitive positions without deciding on the effectiveness of internal transformations.

The efficiency of the innovative model is enhanced by complementarity, synergy, which provides additional benefits that cannot be achieved when the "portfolio of tasks" is a simple sum of individual projects. Synergy is achieved through mutual support and accumulation of results of various ongoing projects. The "portfolio of tasks" to create value for consumers and increase the value of the enterprise can be presented in the form of sequential and parallel implementation.

Therefore, there is a need for effective planning and organization of the lifecycle of the task in order to make timely management decisions, which will reduce the impact of possible disturbances. Unlike most matrix models used for “portfolio” analysis and planning, it is recommended to use the method of dynamic programming in the management of the “portfolio” of the innovative model.

References:

1. Bind, Vyacheslav, Petrukha, Nina & Malashkin, Maksym (2020). Formalization and general methodical concept of cost engineering in the system of crisis management of construction enterprises. *Management of Development of Complex Systems*, 44, 116–127. doi:10.32347/2412-9933.2020.44.116-127.
2. Chupryna, I., Ryzhakova, G., Chupryna, K., Biloshchyt'skyi, A., Tormosov, R. and Gonchar, V. (2022), “Designing a toolset for the formalized evaluation and selection of reengineering projects to be implemented at an enterprise” *Eastern-European Journal of Enterprise Technologies*, vol. 1(13(115)), pp. 6–19. DOI:10.15587/1729-4061.2022.251235
3. Chernyshev, D., Ryzhakova, G., Honcharenko, T., Petrenko, H., Chupryna, I. and Reznik, N. (2022), “Digital Administration of the Project Based on the Concept of Smart Construction”, *Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems*, vol. 495, pp. 1316–1331. DOI:10.1007/978-3-031-08954-1_114
4. Kulikov, P., Ryzhakova, G., Honcharenko, T., Ryzhakov, D. and Malykhina, O. (2020), “OLAP-tools for the formation of connected and diversified production and project management systems”, *International Journal of Advanced Trends in Computer Science and Engineering*, vol. 8(10), pp. 7337–7343. DOI:10.30534/ijeter/2020/1108102020
5. Akselrod, R., Shpakov, A., Ryzhakova, G., Honcharenko, T., Chupryna, I. and Shpakova, H. (2022), “Integration of Data Flows of the Construction Project Life Cycle to Create a Digital Enterprise Based on Building Information Modeling”, *International Journal of Emerging Technology and Advanced Engineering*, vol. 12(1), pp. 40-50. DOI:10.46338/ijetae0122_05
6. Official site of the State Statistics Service of Ukraine (2022), available at: <http://www.ukrstat.gov.ua/> (Accessed 27 June 2022).
7. Revunov, O. M. (2021), “Analytical tools for diagnosing quality management systems of enterprises-stakeholders of construction projects”, *Management of Development of Complex Systems*, vol. 45, pp. 161-169. DOI:10.32347/2412-9933.2021.45.161-169
8. Ryzhakova, G. M. (2021), “Methodological regulation and analytical and information management support of organizations in the modern system of construction development”, *Formuvannya rynkovykh vidnosyn v Ukrayini*, vol. 7-8, pp. 59-65. DOI:10.5281/zenodo.5561124
9. Hryshkevich, O. M. (2020), “Modern paradigm of public investments as a tool of state regulation of sustainable economic development”, *Management of Development of Complex Systems*, vol. 44, pp. 136-142. DOI:10.32347/2412-9933.2020.44.136-142
10. Kucherenko, O. I. (2021), “Scientific and applied components of the formation of a strategy of institutionally oriented diversification of the activity of construction enterprises”, *Management of Development of Complex Systems*, vol. 47, pp. 109-118. DOI:10.32347/2412-9933.2021.47.109-118
11. Ryzhakov, D.A. (2019), “Evaluation of the productivity of the developer's operating system in the microenvironment of housing construction stakeholders”, *Shlyakhy pidvyshchennya efektyvnosti budivnytstva v umovakh formuvannya rynkovykh vidnosyn*, vol. 42, pp. 120–131. DOI:10.32347/2707-501x.2019.42.120-131
12. Akselrod, R.B. and Shpakov, A.V. (2021), “Economic and managerial predictors of transformation of operational systems of construction development in conditions of digitalization of the economy”, *Formuvannya rynkovykh vidnosyn v Ukrayini*, vol. 12, pp. 113-121. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6090221
13. Ryzhakova, G.M., Leshchinska, I.V. and Kistion, D.V. (2019), “General-methodical regulation and analytical and information support of administration processes in the modern system of building development”, *Suchasni problemy arkhitektury ta mistobuduvannya*, vol. 55, pp. 154-168. DOI: 10.32347/2077-3455.2019.55.154-168